

THEORETICAL FOUNDATIONS OF THE ORGANIZATION OF PROFESSIONAL PRACTICE THAT DEVELOPS PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE BY MEANS OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. Vocational practice based on digital technologies plays an important role in the development of professional competences of students of higher educational institutions in the world. Digitization of professional practice is an integral part of the training of highly qualified pedagogues for various types of education, and is a pedagogical process that develops professional skills and qualifications of students.

Keywords: pedagogical process, Educational process, innovation, professional, competence, competence, pedagogical, communication, initiative, individual.

The <https://talaba-amaliyot.fdu.uz/> platform was created at Fergana State University for the digitalization of the professional practice of students in the field of pedagogy. Qualified practice is an integral part of the system of training future pedagogical personnel, and it plays an important role in the formation of professional skills and further development of the future pedagogue. It is known that if the future pedagogue does not have enough theoretical and practical knowledge in the professional direction he has chosen, and he cannot convey it to students during his professional career, that is, if he does not know what he needs to be educated, then today's youth, who are our future, will not be able to become experts at the level of today's demand tomorrow. Therefore, it is necessary for students today to know the tasks of professional practice that are carried out through digital technologies.

During the qualification practice, the following tasks are performed:

- deepening and strengthening students' theoretical knowledge;
- development of the need to acquire independent pedagogical knowledge and constant self-education;
- Cultivating and strengthening interest in the profession of the teacher of "Network Technologies";
- education of important professional qualities of the future teacher;
- formation and development of professional skills and qualifications;
- formation of a creative and research approach to pedagogical activity.

Qualified pedagogical practice organizes the educational process based on the requirements of the time, successfully applies advanced pedagogical and information technologies, has sufficient work experience in this regard, and continuous educational material supply meets today's requirements, is made on the basis of the agreement concluded with general secondary educational institutions. In educational institutions located as close as possible to the territory of the higher educational institution, where qualified pedagogical practice is conducted, interns-students fulfill their rights and obligations to carry out qualified practice. Obligations of the student during the period of qualifying practice in general education schools:

- to comply with school's internal procedures, the order set by school director, deputy school director, practice leaders;
- being equally responsible for the job and its results as school staff;
- compliance with labor discipline;
- full performance of the tasks stipulated in the qualification practice plan;
- observing and studying computer science classes for one week, and participating in the preparatory or final parts of the lesson under the supervision of a science teacher for the second week;
- participation in open classes and group activities;
- for every-day participation in all kinds of activities (observation of classes, participation in classes, holding educational and cultural events, studying documents, etc.) it is mandatory to spend at least 6 hours a day.

Student rights:

- based on school conditions and possibilities, the student should independently draw up an individual work plan for the period of professional practice in accordance with this plan;
- to show creative approach and initiative in organizing educational and creative events;
- getting advice from the stylistic leader, school experts;
- Independent selection of forms, types and topics of educational and extracurricular work on the subject of "Network Technologies";
- when the student's work is considered unsatisfactory, he should apply to the dean to retake the qualification practice without leaving the training. In the process of fulfilling the rights and obligations of professional practice, students of applied mathematics get to know professional activities, acquire professional skills and qualifications, and professional work experience. Students of applied mathematics will get acquainted with the contents of document sets, events, and the preparation of demonstrable weapons prepared during practice.

In general education schools, the computer room should be student and teacher's computer room, organized on a scientific basis, which serves to increase the effectiveness of education.

It is important for students of the field of applied mathematics to go to general education schools for professional practice, to know the requirements for their practice and to get acquainted with professional activities, to acquire professional skills and qualifications.

In the introduction of professional practice on the basis of digital technologies, it is aimed at receiving daily reports of students and developing teachers on the basis of digital technologies. With the help of digital technologies, students are sent to the attached organizations or enterprises for internships, and students post daily activities and reports on the electronic internship platform.

The time of arrival of the students to the practice place is determined and it is necessary to post the work done within 12 hours. If the student cannot post the reports within the specified period, the platform will be closed and the student will be considered absent for the practice on that day.

In addition to conducting internships on time through digital technologies, it is necessary for students to go to the organization to which the internship is attached and write reports. The head of internship in the organization reviews the daily work of the intern students and clicks the confirmation button, thus it becomes easier to control the intern students and the information is posted on the platform in time.

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